

REPAIR OF DAMAGED PRECAST BRIDGE COLUMNS WITH GROUTED SPLICE SLEEVE CONNECTIONS USING CFRP SHELLS AND PLASTIC HINGE RELOCATION

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ABSTRACT

A repair technique has been developed to relocate the column plastic hinge of severely damaged precast reinforced concrete (RC) bridge columns. The technique utilizes a combination of a prefabricated carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) shell with additional wet layup CFRP layers, epoxy anchored headed mild steel bars and nonshrink concrete. Undamaged columns with two different mechanical connector systems were initially tested to failure using cyclic quasi-static lateral loads. One connection system was used to connect a RC bridge pier cap to a column and a second connection system was used to connect a RC footing to a column. Failure of the two original specimens occurred at drift ratios between 6% and 7% with longitudinal bars fracturing in the column plastic hinge region. Subsequently, the column plastic hinge region was repaired by increasing the column cross-section from an octagonal section to a circular section and thus enlarging the column size from 53 cm to 76 cm up to a height equal to 46 cm. The repair was constructed using a prefabricated CFRP shell with additional wet layup CFRP layers. Headed mild steel bars were epoxy anchored into the pier cap and footing inside the CFRP shell. Nonshrink concrete was used to fill the void between the original columns and CFRP shell. Compared to the undamaged assemblies, the repaired specimens failed at the same drift ratio and at greater ultimate lateral loads. The plastic hinge was successfully relocated at the column section adjacent to the repair and the failure mode was bar fracture in the relocated plastic hinge region. The method is a viable technique for seismic repair or seismic retrofit of precast assemblies with severe damage in column to footing or column to pier cap connections.

1 INTRODUCTION

Repairing damaged bridge elements following an earthquake is a viable alternative to replacement. The benefits include cost savings, reduction in construction time and decreased interruption for emergency services and the public. The objective of bridge repair is to rehabilitate the damaged bridge elements to a level similar to the original performance by restoring the load and displacement capacity. Current bridge design philosophy promotes damage to occur in the columns; hence, the post-seismic

repair studied is focused on column repair. In the past, repair techniques for damaged bridge columns included the use of externally bonded CFRP wraps [1-6], steel jackets [7-9], and concrete jackets [10, 11]. However, until recently it has been assumed that when longitudinal bars within the column buckle or fracture the column must be replaced [12].

Accelerated Bridge Construction (ABC) is gaining acceptance because of reduced construction time and minimal traffic interruption. Recently, Grouted Splice Sleeves (GSS) have gained attention as a possible precast concrete connection method for ABC in seismic regions. Current research is investigating the performance of GSS connections for bridges built in seismic regions [13-15]. The use of GSS connections in seismic regions is imminent and a practical post-earthquake repair is needed to accompany this new technology. Findings from the current GSS research indicate that columns connected using GSS concentrate the column damage and decrease the effective plastic hinge length compared to traditional monolithic construction [16]. Both of these characteristics are advantageous for repair purposes, leaving a relatively undamaged column section for plastic hinge relocation.

The repair procedure developed has been designed and implemented on two severely damaged precast specimens connected using GSS. The specimens had undergone quasi-static cyclic testing reaching a final damage state before being repaired. The repair uses materials that are readily available and easy to install including epoxy anchored headed bars, CFRP sheets and nonshrink concrete. The result is a very cost effective and rapid repair procedure, which could be completed in a few days. Due to the robust nature of the repair it is a suitable option for columns with varying damage states.

2 ORIGINAL TEST SPECIMENS

Two precast RC specimens representing half-scale bridge elements, conforming to current seismic bridge design standards were constructed utilizing two different GSS systems [17]. Specimen NM-O is a column-to-footing assembly where the GSS system uses high strength grout on both ends of the connection to splice the bars from the footing and column. Specimen LE-O is a column-to-pier cap assembly where the GSS system has a threaded connection on one end and a grouted connection on the other.

2.1 Original Specimen Reinforcement and Geometry

The geometry and reinforcement of the columns for both NM-O and LE-O is the same, as shown in Fig. 1. The columns are 2.59 m tall with a 53 cm wide octagonal cross section. The longitudinal reinforcement consists of six 25 mm steel bars arranged in a circular pattern which extend out of the column concrete for a length of 18 cm; these steel bars are inserted into the GSS in the footing or pier cap and grouted to complete the connection. A 13 mm steel spiral at a 64 mm pitch provides the transverse reinforcement. The GSS in both cases are outside the column plastic hinge region and are located in the footing and pier cap for NM-O and LE-O, respectively. The footing is 1.83 m long, 61 cm deep and 91 cm wide, as shown in Fig. 1(a). The pier cap is 2.74 m long, 61 cm deep and 61 cm wide, as shown in Fig. 1(b). Material properties of the components and the repair are given in Table 1.

2.2 Testing Assembly and Loading Protocol

Columns in bridges subjected to seismic ground motions experience double curvature bending between the pier cap and footing in the transverse direction. The test assembly, shown in Fig. 2(a), applies a lateral load at a point that represents the approximate inflection point of an actual bridge column. The pier cap specimen was tested upside down, with the pier cap on the strong floor, for ease of testing. The loading consisted of a constant axial load and a displacement controlled cyclic quasi-static lateral load. The axial load applied was 6% of the axial load capacity of the column.

The lateral load was applied following the loading protocol shown in Fig. 2(b). Two cycles per drift ratio were used and the amplitude was progressively increased until a 20% drop in the lateral load capacity was reached [18].

Figure 1. Original specimen reinforcement and geometry: (a) NM-O; (b) LE-O.

Specimen	Bar Properties				Column Concrete Strength	Repair Concrete Strength	CFRP Jacket	
	Longitudinal (D25)		Headed (D25)					
	F_y (MPa)	F_u (MPa)	F_y (MPa)	F_u (MPa)	Test-day (MPa)	Test-day (MPa)	F_u (MPa)	E_j (MPa)
NM-O	469	641	--	--	38	--	--	--
NM-R	469	641	427	593	44	52	689	62052
LE-O	469	641	--	--	41	--	--	--
LE-R	469	641	427	593	42	48.0	689	62052

Table 1. Material Properties

2.3 Original Specimen Test Results

The pre-existing damage state of the original specimens is a critical parameter for the repair design and subsequent performance. The initial test results of NM-O and LE-O are summarized in Table 2 in terms of maximum lateral load, ultimate drift ratio, displacement ductility, reserve capacity, and failure mode. The failure mode for both NM-O and LE-O was fracture of an extreme longitudinal bar. The extreme east longitudinal bar fractured in NM-O and the extreme west longitudinal bar fractured in LE-O. Once the extreme longitudinal bar fractured, which indicates failure, the lateral load capacity of the specimens dropped below 20% of the ultimate load capacity. The reserve lateral load capacity of the original columns after testing was 45% and 43% of the maximum lateral load capacity of NM-O and LE-O, respectively. A very well developed plastic hinge was formed at the footing-to-column and column-to-pier cap interfaces, as shown in Fig. 3, where extensive spalling and cracking occurred. For both specimens, major structural cracking was isolated to three distinct heights from the footing or pier cap interface, where the highest crack was located approximately 36 cm up the column for NM-O and 31 cm up the column for LE-O. These crack widths ranged from 0.4 mm to 1.5 mm.

3 REPAIR DESIGN

The objective of the repair was to strengthen the original plastic hinge region through increasing the column cross section from a 53 cm octagonal section to an additionally reinforced 76 cm diameter circular section. The 76 cm diameter circular cross-section was constructed by filling prefabricated carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) shells with nonshrink concrete and post-installing epoxy

Figure 2. Test Assembly and Loading Protocol: (a) Test Assembly; (b) Loading Protocol.

Test Criteria	NM-O	LE-O
Max Lateral Load (kN)	173	161
Ultimate Drift Ratio (%)	6.42	6.50
Displacement Ductility	6.1	5.8
Reserve Capacity (kN)	95	92
Failure Mode	Bar Fracture	Bar Fracture

Table 2. Original Specimen Test Results

Figure 3. Initial Column Damage: (a) NM-O; (b) LE-O

anchored headed bars for additional tensile reinforcement, as shown in Fig. 4. To form the new plastic hinge, a bending moment referred to as, M_{PH} , must be resisted at the desired plastic hinge location. In the present case, the original specimen test results were used to determine M_{PH} , however, the bending moment can also be found using a sectional analysis. From Eq. (1), the bending moment experienced at the column joint, M_{joint} , is proportional to the length of the repair, H_{rep} , and the height of the column from the point of inflection to the column-footing or column-pier cap joint, H_{col} .

$$M_{joint} = \frac{M_{PH}}{\left(1 - \frac{H_{rep}}{H_{col}}\right)} \quad (1)$$

Similar to the bending moment demand, the shear force demand that must be resisted by the column to achieve plastic hinge relocation, V_{PHR} , is directly related to H_{rep} . This relationship is shown in Eq. (2).

$$V_{PHR} = \frac{M_{PH}}{(H_{col} - H_{rep})} \quad (2)$$

Equations (1) and (2) indicate that using the minimum possible repair height is advantageous for limiting the bending moment and shear demands. However, the height of the repair must be sufficient to relocate the new plastic hinge to a column cross-section which has minimal damage. From the observed damage of the two original specimens shown in Fig. 3, a repair height of 46 cm or 87% of the column cross-section, was determined to be sufficient.

Headed steel bars were designed to develop the increased joint moment, M_{joint} , required for the repair. The headed bar length drilled into the footing or pier cap was determined so that the epoxy anchorage would develop the bars in tension. Similarly, the length of headed bar extending into the repair was checked for adequate development length. These parameters led to the design of six 25 mm headed steel bars which were post-installed around the column as shown in Fig. 4. The embedment into the footing or pier cap was 19 bar diameters and the length extending into the repair was 14 bar diameters. The headed bars used in this design had a head diameter of 27 mm.

The 76 cm diameter repair cross-section utilized a CFRP shell which was designed to provide confinement, shear strength, and was also utilized as stay-in-place formwork for the nonshrink concrete. Four layers of unidirectional CFRP sheets oriented in the hoop direction were provided. Each CFRP layer was 1 mm thick with the properties given in Table 1. One CFRP layer was provided as part of a spliced shell to wrap subsequent layers of CFRP; one CFRP layer was provided to restore the shear strength of the original plastic hinge region; finally, two CFRP layers were provided for confinement and prevention of strain softening; details of the design procedure are provided elsewhere [19-23]. A 13 mm gap was left between the bottom of the CFRP jacket and footing or pier cap surface, as shown in Fig. 4, to ensure there was no bearing of the CFRP shell on the concrete during large displacements.

Figure 4. Repair Design

The shear capacity of the original column should be checked to ensure flexural failure at the location of the relocated plastic hinge. In this case, the transverse steel reinforcement in the relocated plastic hinge was sufficient to ensure a flexural failure mode. If however, the shear capacity of the column were insufficient, additional retrofit measures of the column in the relocated plastic hinge and potentially the whole column length would have been necessary.

3.1 Repair Procedure

The first step of the repair procedure was to create prefabricated CFRP shells. A single layer of 46 cm wide CFRP sheet was wrapped and cured around a 76 cm diameter sonotube to create the proper shape. While the CFRP shell was curing, the holes for the headed bars were core drilled into the footing or pier cap and the headed bars were epoxy anchored into place around the column, as shown in Fig. 5(a). After the CFRP shell had cured it was split in two half cylinders and brought around the column as shown in Fig. 5(b). The sonotube inside the shell in Fig. 5(b) was used to ensure that the shell maintained its shape, while the additional layers of CFRP were applied and was subsequently removed once all CFRP layers had cured. A 31 cm long by 46 cm wide piece of CFRP sheet was used to splice the two halves of the CFRP shell on both sides. Once the first layer of the CFRP shell was spliced, three additional CFRP layers were added as shown in Fig. 5(c). Each layer was 2.54 m long by 46 cm wide, providing 15 cm of overlap for each layer. This was the last step in completing the construction of the CFRP shell which also acted as stay-in-place formwork for the repair nonshrink concrete. Once the CFRP shell had fully cured, nonshrink concrete was added to the space between the column and CFRP shell as shown in Fig. 5(d). For specimen LE-O, the diameter of the repair was larger than the width of the pier cap. Wooden forms were placed alongside the pier cap in order to provide sufficient width for the repair as shown in Figs. 5(b) and 5(c). The forms were removed once the concrete had cured. In practice, the pier cap would be oriented above the column and the gap between the repair and pier cap would provide an inlet for the concrete.

4 REPAIRED SPECIMEN TEST RESULTS

Since the test results of specimens NM-O and LE-O were similar, the same repair design described previously was used for both specimens. The repaired specimens for NM-O and LE-O are referred to as NM-R and LE-R, respectively. The test assembly and loading protocol used to test the original specimens were also used to test the repaired specimens. Plastic hinge relocation was successfully achieved for both NM-R and LE-R, as shown in Fig. 6.

4.1 Specimen NM-R

The hysteretic response of NM-R superimposed with that of NM-O is shown in Fig. 7(a). It can be seen from the hysteretic response and Table 3, that specimen NM-R achieved an 18% larger lateral load than NM-O and had a similar displacement capacity. The failure mode of NM-R was fracture of column longitudinal bars in the relocated plastic hinge region. The extreme west longitudinal bar fractured during the first cycle of the 7.3% drift step and the extreme east longitudinal bar fractured during the second cycle of the same drift. The east longitudinal steel bar fractured only 55 cm above the fracture location of the same bar in NM-O; thus, the repair provided sufficient confinement and

Figure 5. Repair procedure: (a) post installed headed bars; (b) split CFRP shell; (c) CFRP shell around column; (d) CFRP shell filled with nonshrink concrete.

Figure 6. Relocation of plastic hinge: (a) NM-O; (b) NM-R; (c) LE-O; (d) LE-R.

clamping to develop the bar in a shorter distance than predicted. Other major events included onset of significant spalling at a 3.1% drift ratio and CFRP cracking parallel to the fiber direction at a 4.2% drift ratio. The circumferential CFRP crack was located approximately 8 cm below the top of the repair, at the same level as the top of the headed bars, and extended halfway around the jacket circumference on the east side. This is the same side the longitudinal column bar fractured in NM-O1. The hysteretic response of the specimen was unaffected by the circumferential crack in the CFRP.

To further examine the performance of NM-R, the hysteretic energy dissipation and stiffness degradation characteristics were compared to NM-O, as shown in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b), respectively.

Figure 7. Repair test results: (a) NM-R and NM-O; (b) LE-R and LE-O.

Test Criteria	NM-O	NM-R	LE-O	LE-R (Pushover)	LE-R (Cyclic)
Max Lateral Load (kips)	38.8	44.6	37.7	46.8	40.5
Ultimate Drift Ratio (%)	6.42	6.96	6.50	6.88	7.2
Displacement Ductility	6.1	6.0	5.9	6.6	---
Failure Mode	Bar Fracture	Bar Fracture	Bar Fracture	---	Bar Fracture

Table 3. Comparison of test results

Figure 8. NM-R performance comparison: (a) hysteretic energy dissipation; (b) normalized stiffness degradation.

The cumulative energy dissipation of NM-R was slightly greater than NM-O for all drift ratios; at the completion of the 6% drift ratio NM-R had dissipated 15% more energy than NM-O. Similarly, the stiffness degradation characteristics of NM-R and NM-O were very similar when normalized to the 0.5% drift ratio stiffness. The normalized stiffness of NM-R was slightly larger than NM-O at all drift ratios and thus the rate of stiffness degradation was slightly lower. The normalization was carried out to show the true degradation of stiffness because NM-R always had a higher stiffness due to the shorter column length. Both of these parameters further confirm that the repair restored the assembly to a performance level similar to the original condition.

4.2 Specimen LE-R

For specimen LE-R, a monotonic pushover was performed with the loading protocol of Fig. 2(b). The monotonic load was applied to the column in the east direction until a drift ratio of 6.9% was reached. At this point, the column was brought back to its original vertical position and tested according to the loading protocol of Fig. 2(b). The monotonic pushover curve is shown in Fig. 7(b). Although the column was displaced to a drift ratio beyond the ultimate drift ratio of LE-O, no longitudinal bars fractured in the column due to the monotonic nature of loading. There was major spalling on the east side of the column, which is shown in Fig. 6(d) that extended 51 cm up the column and exposed the spiral reinforcement.

With the repaired column already damaged in one direction from the monotonic test, the specimen was subsequently tested cyclically. The hysteretic response of LE-R is shown in Fig. 7(b) with the hysteretic response of LE-O superimposed. The right side of the hysteresis for LE-R shows an

irregular response due to damage from the monotonic test. The left side of the hysteresis is minimally affected; comparisons of the hysteretic response were made with respect to this side of the hysteresis. The failure mode of LE-R was fracture of the extreme east longitudinal bar in the relocated plastic hinge region. The bar fractured during the first cycle of the 7.3% drift step. Similar to the behaviour of NM-R, the onset of significant spalling on the west side of the column occurred at a drift ratio of 3.1% and the onset of transverse CFRP cracking occurred at a drift ratio of 4.2%. The transverse CFRP cracking was located approximately 8 cm below the top of the repair, at the top of the headed bars, and extended halfway around the jacket circumference on the west side. The specimen remained unaffected from the transverse CFRP crack. Due to the initial damage of LE-R1 from the monotonic test it is difficult to directly compare LE-R to LE-O. However, by examining the performance of LE-R in Table 3 from both the monotonic and cyclic tests, it is clear that LE-R performed similarly to LE-O.

4.3 Test Comparison

Table 3 shows a comparison of all the tests. In all cases, the repaired specimens were able to regain the strength of the original specimens while still performing in a ductile manner. For the case of repaired specimen NM-R a 15% increase in the maximum lateral load was achieved at a similar ultimate drift ratio and displacement ductility to the original specimen NM-O. For the case of repaired specimen LE-R it is difficult to make comparisons to original specimen LE-O, because of the initial static pushover test. The performance of LE-R from both the monotonic and cyclic tests, suggests that it performed at least as well as LE-O.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A rapid repair procedure has been developed for severely damaged bridge columns connected using GSS in cyclic tests simulating large earthquakes. The repair converts the original plastic hinge region from a 53 cm octagonal section to a 76 cm diameter circular section thereby relocating the new plastic hinge to a section adjacent to the repair. The repair extends over the column height for a length sufficiently long to include the original plastic hinge region and is reinforced with headed steel bars and a CFRP shell. This repair procedure was implemented and tested for previously damaged bridge column-to-footing and column-to-pier cap joints; it successfully restored the performance of the specimens in terms of displacement and load capacity, displacement ductility, energy dissipation and stiffness. The repair method is a viable technique for seismic repair or retrofit of severely damaged precast GSS columns in column-to-footing or column-to-pier cap connections. The repair method could also be used for columns of existing bridges with additional measures such as improvement of the seismic performance of the column above the relocated plastic hinge.

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